

The Influence Of Strategic ShopeePay, Spaylater, And Cash On Delivery Payment Methods Purchasing Decisions in E-Commerce

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ABSTRACT

This research to determine the influence of the ShopeePay, SpayLater, and Cash on Delivery variables on consumer purchasing decisions. The research was conducted on the Panam community in Pekanbaru City. The type of research used in quantitative research. The sample consisted of 96 people using purposive sampling technique. The data analysis method in this study uses multiple linear regression with the SPSS Statistics Application. The research results show that the ShopeePay variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Y), the SpayLater variable (X2) has no effect on purchasing decisions (Y), and Cash on Delivery (X3) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. (Y).

INTRODUCTION

Online shopping has become popular among the Indonesian public. Online shopping is the process of buying and selling transactions conducted through intermediaries in the form of online shopping sites. Online shopping can also be understood as the consumer's desire to spend their money to obtain something they want from an online store.

According to SimilarWeb data, in Q1 2023, Shopee had 158 million visits, and in Q2, it had 167 million visitors. Meanwhile, Tokopedia had 117 million visits in Q1 and 107.2 million in Q2 of this year. Shopee continues to maintain its dominance in the Indonesian e-commerce market until mid-2023. Based on the survey results above, it shows that Shopee is the most popular and favored e-commerce platform among the Indonesian people.

Shopee offers many features that provide convenience and comfort for its consumers. One of the conveniences offered by Shopee is the ease of making payment transactions. Currently, Shopee e-commerce has provided 10 alternative payment methods for its consumers who want to shop online. The various alternative payment methods offered by Shopee include SeaBank, ShopeePay, COD, COD-Check First, SPaylater, TF Bank, Credit/Debit Card, BRI Direct Debit, BCA OneKlik, and Cash Payment at Partners/Agents. With the availability of various payment alternatives, consumers can choose the payment method that best suits them.

The first payment method is ShopeePay. ShopeePay is a digital wallet service within the Shopee e-commerce platform. using this payment method, consumers can enjoy free shipping, cashback, and other attractive promotions.

This payment method is also considered more practical and efficient because consumers no longer need to provide cash when the goods arrive. Consumers also do not have to wait for their change, as the amount spent online will be directly deducted from their ShopeePay balance.

The second payment method is SPaylater. SPaylater is a payment method that allows for installments without the need for a credit card. In accordance with its tagline "buy now, pay later," which means consumers will receive the goods first and the payment will follow at the beginning of the next month. The bill can be paid within a period of one month or even a year. This payment method is also considered easy, the process is quick, and it offers many attractive promotions. The way to pay the bill is also very easy, simply by choosing a preferred payment method such as ShopeePay.

The third payment method is cash on delivery, or COD. Cash on delivery is a cash payment method where consumers pay when the goods arrive. This COD payment method has become an alternative for online purchases because it is considered safer and more convenient, as it ensures that the items will arrive safely. This payment method is already familiar to those who often shop online. By using this payment method, consumers can minimize fraud, so first-time users no longer need to worry about their items not being delivered.

LITERATURE RESEARCH

According to Kotler and Armstrong in purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior, which is the study of how a consumer selects, buys, and uses goods or services to satisfy their needs and desires. According to Kotler and Keller, purchasing decisions involve the integration of knowledge to consider two or more options in order to choose one among them.

According to Nurliyanti et al., the purchasing decision is the process by which consumers determine which product to buy by seeking information about several products and considering which item is better.

It can be concluded that purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior as a form of selection or consideration in buying goods or services to meet their needs and desires. In purchasing decisions, consumers are faced with two or more product options that are offered. Consumers should compare and consider which products meet their needs and desires. Once the decision is made, consumers will make a purchase in order to consume the product.

A. Payment Method

Payment methods are ways for consumers to pay for something. Various payment methods can be options for consumers when shopping, both cash and non-cash. As the most popular e-commerce platform in Indonesia, it offers various payment methods that can be used as alternative payment options to make it easier for its consumers to make online purchases.

Each payment method offered has its own advantages and disadvantages. The ease of transactions, free shipping, discounts and promotions, instalment options, and other attractive offers are highly appreciated by consumers. With this in mind, the consumer will choose the payment method they prefer to make the online purchase.

Putri et al. (2019) stated that the availability of alternative payment methods in e-commerce can influence a consumer's purchasing decisions.

B. ShopeePay of Definition

ShopeePay is an electronic wallet service that serves as one of the payment methods on Shopee and also for offline payments at partnered merchants, as well as being able to store refunds that can be used for future transactions.

ShopeePay is a digital wallet that can be used as one of the payment methods in Shopee e-commerce. From the various explanations above, it can be concluded that ShopeePay is one of the digital wallet services available in Shopee e-commerce. Customers can use ShopeePay to conduct online shopping transactions on the Shopee e-commerce platform, including outside of Shopee. The funds will be stored and can be used to carry out the next transaction. Thus, the customer service does not need to hassle about resending the item when it arrives and does not need to process a refund, as it will be directly deducted from the ShopeePay balance.

ShopeePay also has a limitation, which is that it does not have its own application. The main function of ShopeePay is to facilitate transactions on Shopee, so it cannot be used for other digital payments, unlike Ovo,

Dana, and Gopay. However, ShopeePay remains popular with the public because each payment model has its own advantages and disadvantages.

C. SPaylater Defenition

Paylater is an alternative payment method that uses an online installment system without requiring a credit card. According to OJK, SPaylater provides a service purchased by Shopeel in the form of a balance so that its users can receive products first and pay later. The payment system can be done at the beginning of the following month after the goods are received.

SPaylater is a payment method in the form of installments without requiring a credit card. Payment using SPaylater offers convenience for paying bills within a period of one month or more. From the definition above, it can be concluded that SPaylater is an alternative method of installment payment, but it does not require a credit card. The buyer will receive the desired item first, while the payment will be made at the beginning of the following month. This is in line with its tagline, "bully now, pay later." Installments can be paid within a period of one month or more, depending on the preference of the borrower. The current situation can only be resolved by understanding the consumer's behavior in the context of online shopping transactions. The existence of payment difficulties in the form of installment payments allows consumers to obtain the goods they desire earlier, while the payments continue.

The benefits of using SPaylater payment are as follows: Easy installments without a credit card, Can help in emergencies, Easy fund borrowing, Low interest rates, No admin fees

Official, Meanwhile, the drawbacks of using SPaylater payment are as follows: Balance cannot be withdrawn, Only usable at Shopee, Penalties for late payments, Limited loan amount

D. Cash On Delivery (COD) Defenition

Cash on delivery is a payment method that is made in cash when the goods are received by the customer. This payment method ensures that products are delivered safely to the address, thus helping customers who want to shop online.

COD is a payment method where the customer will pay in cash when the courier has delivered the goods. Cash on Delivery is a payment method where the customer pays for the product in cash when the goods have arrived at the address. This payment method has become an alternative for online shopping payments because it is considered safer and more convenient, and the delivery of goods is guaranteed.

This payment model has several advantages, namely being easy and effective, providing returns, and minimizing errors. However, cash on delivery also has drawbacks, such as the frequent occurrence of cases that harm the seller. The customer canceled the service during COD while it was in progress, so the courier did not receive the previously agreed-upon return item. The next issue is when the item ordered does not match what the customer expected, then the customer who does not understand online shopping does not want to pay the seller. Actually, they should have paid first, then logged into the online store where they made the purchase to request a refund for the money or the item.

The indicators of Cash on Delivery (COD) are: The security of payments because they are made in person, thus minimizing the risk of online shopping, The privacy of data is maintained, Consumer trust is increasingly enhanced.

Table 1. Previous Research

No	Author Name	Heading	Result
1.	Wahyu Suryo Agung Prabowo (2023)	Pelngarulh ShopeelPay, Testimony on the Advertisement Regarding the Purchase Experience on the Shopeel Application (Case Study on the Community of Tarakan City)	ShopeePay, Testimonials, and Ads significantly influence Variable the purchasing decisions of users on the Shopee application.

2.	Widiawati Susanti, Rronny Malavia Mardani, Andi Normaladewi (2023)	The Influence of Bullying Impulses, Prices, and ShopeePay Treatment on Customer Satisfaction (Case Study on Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at the Islamic University of Malang)	Impulse Buying significantly affects purchasing decisions. Price significantly influences purchasing decisions. Shopee Paylater also has a significant influence on purchasing decisions.
3	Diansyah, Winny Novanda Putri (2023)	The Influence of Shopee Paylater and Member Facilities on Online Purchase Decisions on Shopee with Shopee Games as Moderation	Shopee Paylater has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. Member facilities have an influence on purchasing decisions. Shopee games can strengthen the influence of member facilities on purchasing decisions, but the interaction of Shopee games can weaken the influence of Shopee Paylater on purchasing decisions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population in this study is the residents of Pekanbaru city are located in the Panam area. Because the population of residents in the Panam area of Pekanbaru City who use the ShopeePay, SPaylater, and Cash on Delivery (COD) payment methods is unknown. Then the researcher used the Lemelshow formula to determine the sample size.

Therefore, the minimum sample size to be taken in this research is 96 people. However, the researcher increased it to 100 respondents.

The criteria for sample selection in this study are:

1. 1.Respondents are residents of the city of Pekanbaru who are in the Panam area
2. 2.Respondents have a Shopee account
3. 3.Respondents have made purchases on the Shopee e-commerce platform using ShopeePay, SPaylater, and Cash On Delivery payment methods (COD).

A. Techniques Data Collection

The Kuesioner is used to analyze the use of ShopeePay, SPaylater, and Cash On Delivery (COD) payment methods on the purchasing satisfaction of Shopee users in the Panam area of Pekanbaru City.

Documentation, The results of the research conducted will be increasingly credible or trust worthy if supported by accompanying documents during the research process. Due to this, the author uses a documentary data collection technique to accurately reflect the actual conditions when the researcher conducts research in the Panam area of Pekanbaru City.

B. Techniques Data Analysis

1. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is used to examine the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables presented in the form of a regression equation. This analysis is conducted to determine the presence or absence of the influence of the variables ShopeePay, SPaylater, and Cash On

Delivery (COD) on the purchasing decisions in the Shopeel e-commerce platform among the Panam community in Pekanbaru City.

2. Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination (R²) represents the extent of the contribution of independent variables to the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to determine the influence of the variables ShopeePay (X1), SPaylater (X2), Cash On Delivery (X3) on Purchase Satisfaction. (Y).

RESULTS

A. Data Quality Test

The purpose of this data quality test is to determine the limits of accuracy of a measuring instrument (questionnaire) which can be conducted as follows:

B. Validity Test

The Validity Test for each statement of the Purchase Decision variable (Y), ShopeePay (X1), SpayLater (X2), and Cash On Delivery (X3) shows that the Corrected Item-Total Correlation or calculated r value for each variable is > 0.2006. This shows that the data is valid because it meets the assumptions of the Validity Test.

C. Reliability Test

A reliability test is a test to determine the consistency of a measuring instrument in its use. The criteria for the reliability test is to observe the Cronbach’s alpha (α) value for each variable. A variable is considered reliable if the Cronbach’s alpha value > 0.60.

Table 2. Reliability Test

No.	Variabel	Cronbach’s alpha	Tanda	Nilai	Keterangan
1.	Purchase Decision (Y)	0,775	>	0,60	Reliabel
2.	ShopeePay (X1)	0,753	>	0,60	Reliabel
3.	SpayLater (X2)	0,796	>	0,60	Reliabel
4.	Cash On Delivery (X3)	0,819	>	0,60	Reliabel

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Cronbach’s Alpha value for each variable in the study is > 0.60. This indicates that each variable is reliable and suitable for testing.

D. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Quantitative analysis methods used to understand the relationship between one or more independent variables and the dependent variable. This analysis is used to prove the presence or absence of the influence of the variables ShopeePay, SpayLater, and Cash on Delivery on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce.

Based on the regression equation, the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable in this study can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of 5.334 with a positive value means that if the independent variable is assumed to be zero (0), the purchase decision variable (Y) has a fixed value of 5.334.
2. The regression coefficient value for the ShopeePay variable (X1) is positive, at 0.367. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the ShopeePay variable, the value of the purchase decision variable will increase by 0.367 units, assuming the values of other independent variables remain constant. In other words, the ShopeePay variable contributes 0.367 or 36.7% to the purchase decision variable.
3. The value of the regression coefficient for the SpayLater variable (X2) is positive, amounting to 0.042. This means that every increase of 1 unit in the gSpayLater variable will increase the value of the purchase decision variable by 0.042 units, assuming the values of other independent variables remain

constant. In other words, the SpayLater variable contributes 0.042 or 4.2% to the purchase decision variable.

- The value of the regression coefficient for the cash on delivery variable (X3) is positive, amounting to 0.330. This means that every increase of 1 unit in the cash on delivery variable will increase the value of the purchase decision variable by 0.330 units, assuming other independent variables remain constant. In other words, the cash on delivery variable contributes 0.330 or 33% to the purchase decision variable.

E. T-Test (Uji Parsial)

Table 3. T-Test (Uji Parsial)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.334	2.029		2.629	.010
	Total X1	.367	.096	.350	3.824	.000
	Total X2	.042	.084	.046	.507	.613
	Total X3	.330	.068	.422	4.859	.000

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

From the table above, the analysis is as follows:

- The ShoopeyPay variable (X1) has a t-value (3.824) > t-table (1.98609) and a significance value (0.000) < (0.05), so Ha is accepted, meaning there is a positive and significant influence of the ShoopeyPay variable on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.
- The SpayLater variable (X2) has a t-value (0.507) < t-table (1.98609) and a significance value (0.613) > (0.05), so Ha is rejected and H0 is accepted, meaning the SpayLater variable does not have a significant influence on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.
- The cash on delivery variable (X3) has a t-value (4.859) > t-table (1.98609) and a significance value (0.000) < (0.05), so Ha is accepted, meaning there is a positive and significant influence of the cash on delivery variable on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.

F. F Test (Uji Simultan)

The F table value in this study is 2.703. The alpha value used is 0.05. The decision-making criterion used is that if F calculated > F table or Sig < a (0.05), then Ha is accepted, meaning there is a joint effect between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Table 4. F Test (Uji Simultan)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	194.872	3	64.957	25.100	.000 ^b
	Residual	238.087	92	2.588		
	Total	432.958	95			

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the calculated F value (25.100) > table F value (2.703) and the significance value (0.000) < 0.05. This indicates that Ha is accepted, meaning that the variables ShopeePay, SpayLater, and Cash On Delivery simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the Panam community in Pekanbaru City.

G. Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

The coefficient of determination test (R2) aims to determine how well a model can explain the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination (R2) ranges between zero and one, indicating how well the independent variables can explain the dependent variable. A good regression model is one where the R2 value approaches 1, indicating that the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables.

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.671	.450	.432	1.609

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, the results of the coefficient of determination test show that the R Square value is 0.450 or 45%. This indicates that the overall independent variables in the study contribute to the dependent variable by 45%. Meanwhile, the remaining (100% - 45% = 55%) is explained by other variables not included in this study.

The Influence of ShopeePay (X1) on Purchase Decisions (Y)

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, it was found that the ShopeePay variable has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Where the calculated t value (3.824) > table t value (1.98609) and the significance value (0.000) < (0.05), the first hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is a positive and significant influence of online customer reviews on purchasing decisions in the Shopee e-commerce platform among the Panam community in Pekanbaru City.

This shows that the better the use of the ShopeePay payment method by consumers, the more it can influence the purchasing decisions of other consumers.

The Influence of SpayLater (X2) on Purchase Decisions (Y)

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test, it was found that the SpayLater variable does not affect the purchasing decision. Where the calculated t value (0.507) < table t value (1.98609) and the significance value (0.613) > (0.05), the second hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is no influence of the SpayLater variable on purchasing decisions in the Shopee e-commerce platform among the Panam community in Pekanbaru City. All consumers using Shopee E-Commerce do not use SpayLater as a payment method for transactions.

The Influence of Cash On Delivery (X3) on Purchase Decisions (Y)

Based on the results of the third hypothesis test, it was found that the Cash On Delivery variable has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Where the calculated t value (4.859) > table t value (1.98609) with a significance value (0.000) < (0.05), the third hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is a positive and significant influence of cash on delivery on purchasing decisions in the Shopee e-commerce platform among the Panam community in Pekanbaru City.

Cash on delivery is a service provided to consumers with a focus on prioritizing security, comfort, and the privacy of consumers' personal data during the online transaction process. This way, consumers do not need to worry about fraud because the goods are paid for upon delivery to the consumer. This payment method is also considered the easiest and most convenient, so consumers who do not have a bank account or who are not near stores that have partnered with Shopee can still make purchases online. This, of course, makes consumers feel facilitated in making online purchases on the Shopee e-commerce platform.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results that have been conducted, the conclusions of this study are as follows:

1. The ShopeePay variable partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.
2. The SpayLater variable partially does not have a significant effect on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.
3. Cash On Delivery partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.
4. The ShopeePay, Spaylater, and Cash On Delivery variables simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in Shopee e-commerce among the people of Panam, Pekanbaru City.

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